

1 **Global slowdown in community turnover**
2 **despite accelerating climate change**

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14 **Global slowdown in community turnover**

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16 **When the species composition of ecological communities changes over time,**
17 **environmental changes are often invoked as the most plausible explanation¹⁻⁴. Several**
18 **lines of reasoning, however, suggest that such compositional change, called temporal**
19 **species turnover, can similarly result from intrinsic ecosystem dynamics in a constant**
20 **environment^{5,6}. The degree to which these two drivers contribute to observed turnover**
21 **remains unclear. Analysing the well-established BioTIME database⁷ of surveys, we show**
22 **that, surprisingly, species turnover has decelerated in more ecosystems over the last 100**
23 **years than it has accelerated. Turnover rates typically declined by one third. In view of**
24 **accelerating environmental change, we had expected species turnover to accelerate if**
25 **environmental drivers dominate,⁸ and to remain constant in the case of strong intrinsic**
26 **drivers. We argue that, with intrinsic dynamics dominating, the observed slowing of**
27 **turnover can be understood as resulting from anthropogenic pressures^{3,9-11} that generate**
28 **effects including environmental degradation or declines of regional species pools¹². Our**
29 **results suggest that observed past changes in species composition were often**
30 **manifestations of natural, intrinsic ecosystem dynamics. Although one must expect**
31 **environmental drivers to dominate species turnover eventually as climate change**
32 **accelerates further, for now such attribution should be done with caution.**

33 Temporal species turnover, the phenomenon of changes in species composition within an
34 ecological community over time, is a widely observed aspect of ecology^{1-3,6,13-17}. The factors
35 that drive temporal species turnover are varied, including environmental changes and intrinsic
36 biotic interactions. For environmental change to drive species turnover at a given location, it
37 has to be beneficial to some species while being detrimental to others. We shall here use the
38 term environmental change in this narrow sense, thus distinguishing it from environmental
39 degradation detrimental to all or most species.

40 Ecologists are divided over the extent to which environmental changes and intrinsic
41 biotic interaction drive species turnover^{1-6,13,14,18,19}. Environmental change can drive species
42 turnover by altering the ecological niche provided by an ecosystem^{2,3,18}. Changes in
43 temperature, precipitation, and other climatic variables can have direct effects on species (such
44 as changes in growth rates, immune response and reproductive patterns²⁰) and indirect effects,
45 causing changes in species interactions (such as the availability of resources that species rely
46 on¹⁹), potentially leading to other species, better adapted to the new conditions, invading,
47 replacing native species, and driving them to local extinction. Yet, previous studies of the
48 impact of environmental change on turnover have yielded inconclusive results¹². For instance,
49 a comprehensive global analysis of the biodiversity effects of local temperature changes on
50 community composition revealed a statistically significant increase of the number of species
51 gained by communities with warming in already relatively warm marine ecosystems, but no
52 such signal for colder marine or terrestrial systems or for species losses². A recent meta-
53 analysis of marine, freshwater and terrestrial community time series in Europe showed no
54 significant effects of the rates of temperature or precipitation change on turnover rates and yet
55 evidence for acceleration of turnover over the last 20-40 years¹³. However, when characterizing
56 community composition in terms of the average preferred temperature of species, clear
57 temporal trends or correlations with local temperature trends can be found^{21,22}. Reasons for

58 such ambiguity are, amongst others, that the relevant environmental variables are difficult to
59 pinpoint, and that combined time series of populations and environmental data of sufficient
60 length are rare and of varying quality²³. Despite these mixed results, it is generally agreed that
61 environmental change can lead to increased rates of turnover in ecological communities,
62 particularly when changes are large or sustained over long periods^{2,3,9,24,25}.

63 Alternatively, species turnover, resulting in dynamic and naturally ever-changing
64 ecosystems, can be driven by intrinsic processes, including ecological drift²⁶, evolution driven
65 by species interactions²⁷, or a combination of species interactions and migration. The latter
66 mechanism⁵ operates as follows: if the regional species pool is large enough, some species
67 from the regional pool will always be able to colonise a local community. Such colonisations
68 then lead to disturbance of the local community, mediated by a complex network of species
69 interactions (e.g., competition and predation), which can result in the extinction of other
70 species⁵. Often the species going extinct will have been locally rare and their decline will be
71 slow²⁸. As a consequence of this restructuring, the community then becomes open to
72 colonisation by other species from the regional species pool, such that the resulting turnover
73 continues without end or direction in a kind of giant “rock-paper-scissors game”²⁹. The
74 celebrated Theory of Island Biogeography¹⁵ and its later generalisation to spatially extended
75 communities¹⁶ predicts a similar kind of non-directional turnover in community composition
76 with apparently random species colonisations and extirpations, although the theory does not
77 specify the precise nature of its drivers¹⁶. Such ongoing non-directional turnover has since been
78 documented on a decadal scale for island bird communities, with indications for potential
79 directional change, characteristic of environmental drivers, arising only on a century time
80 scale⁶. Intrinsically driven recurrent local turnover is also the mechanism thought to explain
81 ‘shifting mosaic’ spatiotemporal community patterns^{17,30}.

82 There is thus an ongoing debate about the relative contributions of environmental and
 83 intrinsic drivers to community turnover in nature. To help resolve this debate, we analysed the
 84 BioTIME database⁷ of timeseries of community composition based on the following
 85 consideration: since climate change is accelerating worldwide, we hypothesise that, if
 86 environmental change is the primary driver of turnover, turnover will generally accelerate as
 87 the rate of climate change accelerates through time⁸. Conversely, if turnover rates remain
 88 unchanged over time, this suggests that intrinsic processes are the dominating driver of
 89 turnover.

90 The BioTIME database includes community composition datasets with considerable
 91 temporal extent (up to 44 years, median 7 years) and spatial coverage (Fig. 1). We partitioned
 92 the studies covering more than 96km² following a previously described spatial data partitioning
 93 protocol^{1,2}. The spatial distribution and type of the partitioned communities is illustrated in
 94 Fig. 1.

95
 96 Figure 1. The distribution and types of communities used in this study. The size
 97 of each pie indicates the number of records of species observations.
 98 Communities are grouped using a leader clustering algorithm³¹ with a 2000km
 99 radius.

100 To address the heterogeneity and variable quality of the studies compiled in the
101 BioTIME database, we developed a methodology that is statistically robust while retaining
102 high statistical power. Our method is based on species presence/absence data (Fig. 2a) to avoid
103 a loss of statistical power associated with domination of metric values by a few abundant
104 species. To quantify changes in ecological communities over time, we used a particular
105 measure of community similarity, the Ochiai metric³², which is known to have low sensitivity
106 to the presence of rare species and be robust to variation in sampling effort³³⁻³⁵. To guard
107 against pseudo turnover³⁶⁻³⁹, which arises when species that are present at a site are overlooked
108 in some sampling campaigns, we did not work directly with the community similarity between
109 subsequent surveys (corresponding to lag 1 in Fig. 2c). Instead, we quantified turnover rate as
110 the rate by which, on average, community similarity decreased with the lag between surveys,
111 using lags from 1 to 5 years (Figs. 2b, c). Rather than attempting, for example, to fit regression
112 models for the dependence of turnover rate on sampling year to the data, we simply compared
113 turnover rates before and since a given ‘breakpoint year’ thought to mark the onset of
114 accelerating climate change. To sidestep uncertainty regarding the question which year this is,
115 we repeated our analysis for breakpoint years from 1932 to 2014.

116 Specifically, we computed by how much, for a given surveyed community, the mean
117 turnover rate since the breakpoint year differed from that before this breakpoint, excluding
118 community time series whose temporal coverage did not include at least five survey years
119 before and after the breakpoint. From this, we then computed the median change in turnover
120 rate over all surveys and, to test for statistical significance, the ‘exact’ confidence interval of
121 this³⁵. We used the median, rather than the mean, to improve robustness against outlier studies.
122 (We caution that dependence of results on breakpoint year cannot be interpreted as an
123 accelerating or decelerating change in turnover rate because the set of studies evaluated
124 depends on the breakpoint year, amongst other reasons.)

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Figure 2. **Methodology and result of estimating median changes in turnover rate**

across breakpoints. a) shows the distribution of temporal changes in community

composition for a temperate bird community⁴⁰ (BioTIME Study ID: 46); b)

community similarity for surveys separated by a lag of one year (lag 1) and five years

(lag 5), with mean similarities indicated by dashed lines; c) the turnover rate

computed as the slope of the decline of mean similarity with lag over 1 – 5-year lags;

d) for illustration, the difference (change) in the overall median turnover rates before

and since a breakpoint year in 1985. Panel e) shows the final result, the median change

in turnover rate for each break year (circles) and 95% confidence intervals (bars) –

for almost all breakpoint years with significant change, this change is negative,

implying decelerating turnover. For sample sizes and p-values, see Extended Data

Table 1. In panel (f), for comparison, black circles and the smooth (with 90%

confidence range) show changes in temperature anomaly⁴¹ (°C) through time,

indicating that climate change started to accelerate around 1975.

140 We noticed that some communities surveyed earlier than 1927 displayed substantial
141 turnover in the early years, which may be an artefact of the early stage of evolving ecological
142 survey techniques, skills, and interests. Hence, data from survey dates in each time series earlier
143 than 1927 were filtered out (38,003 observations). Overall, we analysed 7,160,857 records of
144 species observations from 371 studies comprising 30,245 species and seven guilds (plants, fish,
145 birds, mammals, reptiles, invertebrates, benthic and mixed communities) from freshwater,
146 marine, and terrestrial ecosystems.

147 Much to our surprise, we found that for nearly all choices of breakpoint year where our
148 analysis could demonstrate a statistically significant change in median turnover rate at all, this
149 change was negative. That is, despite accelerating climate change (Figure 2f), community
150 turnover tended to decelerate (Figure 2d, e). The only exception to this, the 1956 breakpoint
151 (Fig. 2d), disappeared when we repeated the analyses using different community similarity
152 metrics or lags longer than 5 years to compute turnover rates (Extended Data Figs. 1, 2). For
153 the remaining statistically significant cases, median change values ranged from -0.0130 to
154 -0.0007 per year (median over all breakpoint years: -0.0019), which is considerable compared
155 to the corresponding median overall turnover rates of all studies included for a given breakpoint
156 year, which ranged from 0.0047 to 0.0131 per year (median: 0.0055). The sample sizes for
157 these breakpoint years (i.e., the number of separate community time series contributing to
158 medians) ranged from 119 to 2970 (mean of 1354). For early breakpoints (period 1933 - 1977)
159 and very late breakpoints we found no clear statistical signal of change in turnover rate, which
160 is expected from the small amount of data available either before or since the breakpoint
161 (Extended Data Table 1). Testing the robustness of these result for other metrics of community
162 similarity (Extended Data Fig. 1) and considering community change over lags longer than five
163 years (Extended Data Fig. 2), we found very similar patterns in the overall results.

164 Our analysis thus suggests that climate change was not the dominant driver of species
165 turnover in the late 20th century. Instead, it implies that turnover may have been driven mainly
166 by intrinsic ecological processes. To explain the unexpected decline in turnover rate amid
167 accelerating environmental changes, we devised a simple numerical community model that
168 accounts not only for the combined effects of environmental change and intrinsic dynamics on
169 community turnover but also for the population dynamical effects of a hypothesised overall
170 environmental degradation (Box 1). We modelled the intensity of environmental degradation
171 by a simple overall reduction of the population growth rates of species in the absence of
172 competition. In reality, this could correspond to a combination of different anthropogenic
173 pressures including habitat destruction or environmental pollution.

174 Compared to a baseline scenario without environmental change or degradation, we find
175 that environmental change accelerates community turnover in the model, while environmental
176 degradation leads to slower turnover on average. The two effects balance each other for certain
177 combinations of environmental change and degradation so that the turnover rate does not
178 change. The slowing of turnover with environmental degradation is intuitively understood from
179 the fact that the number of species that can occupy the modelled site decreases with
180 degradation, and hence the number of potential invaders driving turnover.

181 The simulations of the model confirm that, if environmental change was the dominant
182 driver of community turnover, our findings from analysis of the BioTIME database⁸ would be
183 hard to explain (Box 1). It is more plausible to interpret our results as evidence that, on a
184 background of intrinsic turnover dynamics, the increasing cumulative effect of various forms
185 of environmental degradation dominated over accelerating environmental change in affecting
186 the rate of ecological community turnover^{11,42}. Moreso, environmental pollution arising from
187 the production, use and disposal of pesticides, pharmaceuticals and heavy metals has been
188 implicated in impacting reproductive physiology, sexual communication, sexual selection and

189 parental care⁹. These environmental pollutants have ecological and evolutionary consequences
190 for the populations exposed to them¹⁰. The attribution of decelerating turnover to the intensity
191 of environmental degradation is consistent with a study of turnover in bird communities in a
192 tropical Andes conservation hot spot⁴³ that concluded: “It is striking that the less altered habitat,
193 native forest, has a higher rate of composition change than the more altered shrub and
194 introduced forest habitats.”

195 Climate-driven changes in community composition may not be as common as
196 previously thought. In the future, however, one can expect the effect of environmental change
197 on community turnover to become stronger¹³. Directional trends in shifts of species ranges
198 consistent with climatic forcing are now well documented⁴⁴⁻⁴⁶ and these will inevitably
199 contribute to local community turnover²³. The fact that these trends emerge from a background
200 of apparent idiosyncrasy in range shifts, where many species shift their ranges in a direction
201 opposite to what is expected from climate change, is consistent with our conclusion that
202 changes in local species composition are driven to a large part by intrinsic dynamics that cause
203 apparently idiosyncratic colonization and extirpations.

204 There may be other, yet-to-be-identified explanations that could account for global
205 slowing of community turnover. These include factors such as improved environmental
206 management and changes in sampling methodology, which could affect the accuracy of data
207 collected on species turnover over time. Other factors that can contribute to a slowing of
208 community turnover include a decline of the regional species pool^{5,12}, a decrease in the
209 interaction strength between species⁴⁷, or environmental heterogeneity resulting from habitat
210 fragmentation^{3,5}. Since the specific causes of the slowing of community turnover may be
211 complex and multifaceted, we suggest further investigation of this phenomenon. If, for
212 example, environmental degradation or loss of regional species pools are the main drivers, this
213 may be cause for concern.

214 Overall, our study highlights the importance of understanding the drivers of species
215 turnover for the interpretation of biodiversity dynamics on a changing planet. Species turnover
216 can be a natural phenomenon indicative of a healthy environment, a large regional species pool,
217 and good connectivity between patches with similar habitats. Change to turnover rates can also
218 be the result of disruption of communities by directed environmental change, although our
219 study suggests that this was not the dominating driver in the past century. By identifying the
220 underlying causes, we can develop more effective strategies for assessing and managing our
221 natural environment.

Box 1. We developed a numerical community model (a) that explains the unexpected decline in turnover rate (b, c) in the face of accelerating environmental changes. Our model takes into account the combined effects of environmental change and intrinsic dynamics, as well as the population dynamics resulting from a hypothesized overall environmental degradation. To represent this degradation, we reduced the population growth rate in the absence of competition for all species by the same amount. From simulated community timeseries as shown in (b), with species differentiated by colour and line style, we compute the turnover rate applying the same method as used for empirical data (c). Our model shows that turnover slows down as the environment degrades and increases with faster environmental change (d). The transparent horizontal plane in (d) represents the turnover rate without environmental change or degradation for comparison. Equation (a) describes a Lotka-Volterra competition model for $S = 1470$ species. B_i stands for the biomass of species $i = 1, \dots, S$; r_i for its intrinsic growth rate under optimal conditions, sampled randomly with mean 1 and standard deviation 0.25; d (varied between 0 and 0.5) represents the constant environmental degradation; and the term involving \sin^2 the environmental preferences of species, with species' preferred niches x_i spaced evenly between zero and one. We modelled niches using a sin function to avoid boundary effects at $x = 0, 1$ that would complicate interpretation of results. The environment changes with a rate v (varied from 0 to 0.6). The A_{ij} represent competition coefficients and $\epsilon = 10^{-20}$ a weak rain of propagules that permits species to re-invade after their effective local extinction. Following Ref. ²⁸, we randomly set the competition coefficients A_{ij} to 0.4 with probability 0.4 or otherwise set them to 0, except for the intraspecific competition coefficients A_{ii} , which we all set to 1 for simplicity.

223 **Methods**

224 The formula for the Ochiai index of community similarity is:

$$225 \quad \text{Ochiai index} = \frac{a}{\sqrt{(a+b)(a+c)}},$$

226 where a is the number of species shared by the two communities, b the number of species
227 unique to the first community, and c the number of species unique to the second community.

228 One advantage of the Ochiai index over other metrics of community similarity is that it is less
229 sensitive to the presence of rare species and more robust to sampling effort^{48,49}. This makes it
230 particularly useful for studies based on large, heterogeneous datasets^{32,33} like the BioTIME
231 database⁷. The Ochiai index has been shown to perform well across a range of community
232 types and ecosystems, including both plant and animal communities, marine and freshwater
233 habitats, and terrestrial ecosystems^{33,34,49}.

234 To test the robustness of our findings, we repeated our analyses using other metrics of
235 community similarity (e.g. Jaccard and Sørensen) implemented within the ade4 R package⁵⁰
236 and examined community change over lags l longer than five years (SI file 1). In this case, we
237 retained only studies that reported l surveys both before and since a given breakpoint year. In
238 addition, we repeated the analysis after removing from the published data partitioning
239 protocol,^{1,2} a step filtering for 'sample completeness'. Results remained essentially unchanged
240 (Extended Data Fig. 3).

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242 **Simulation of changes in turnover rate in response to environmental change and** 243 **degradation**

244 We developed a numerical model (Box 1a) to elucidate the unexpected decline observed in the
245 turnover rate (Box 1b, c) when faced with rapidly changing environmental conditions. The
246 simulation was conducted over 4000 unit times with the sampling interval ('year') given by 25
247 unit times. A burn-in period of 400 unit times was employed to allow the system to reach a

248 steady state before data collection. To determine the community turnover rate for each scenario
249 of environmental change and environmental degradation, we utilized the method described for
250 empirical data analysis, classifying all those species i as present whose simulated biomass B_i
251 exceeded 0.01 (SI file 2). We simulated this model in a full-factorial design with 20-fold
252 replication, varying the intensity of environmental degradation d from 0 to 0.5 in 20 steps and
253 the environmental rate of change v from 0 to 0.6 in 20 steps (totalling 8000 model runs). Panel
254 (d) in Box 1 shows a full third-order multivariate polynomial fit to the dependence of turnover
255 rate on d and v . The Akaike Information Criterion preferred this third-order fit over a second-
256 or fourth-order fit.

257

258 **Data availability**

259 The data that support the findings of this study were sourced from the BioTIME database⁷.

260

261 **Code availability**

262 The R code used for data analysis and simulation is provided as Supplementary Information.

263

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273 **Author contributions**

274 AGR designed the study, AGR and ECN developed and tested the methods, performed data
275 analyses and wrote the manuscript. MFS contributed to contextualization and improving the
276 manuscript.

277

278 **Competing interests**

279 The authors declare no competing interests.

280

281 **Materials & Correspondence**

282 Correspondence to E. C. Nwankwo and A. G. Rossberg.

283

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401 **Extended Data Table 1. Median change in community turnover rate per year across**
 402 **different breakpoint years, with 95% confidence intervals, sample sizes *n*, and p-values**

Breakpoint year	median	lower CI	upper CI	<i>n</i>	p-value
1932	-0.0184114	-0.0318738	0.00211278	16	0.076812744
1933	-0.0063375	-0.0365392	0.00608014	18	0.096252441
1934	-0.0047382	-0.014988	0.00325751	18	0.237884521
1935	-0.0040422	-0.0222078	0.00566982	19	0.167068481
1936	-0.0051959	-0.0128742	0.00040346	20	0.503444672
1937	-0.0040153	-0.0161517	0.00435076	21	0.078353882
1938	-0.0021192	-0.0115462	0.00588876	34	0.607591361
1939	-0.0001784	-0.0080722	0.00668632	50	1
1940	0.00011074	-0.0055288	0.00767697	86	1
1941	-0.0008041	-0.0055288	0.00733276	86	0.913202362
1942	-0.0015875	-0.0057178	0.00733276	85	0.826404724
1943	-0.0015875	-0.0057178	0.00733276	85	0.826404724
1944	-0.0010813	-0.0062455	0.00733276	87	0.66464549
1945	-0.0001039	-0.0062455	0.00767697	87	0.828423274
1946	-5.24E-05	-0.0055288	0.00732947	98	0.918778035
1947	-0.0007212	-0.0077352	0.00636281	98	0.918778035
1948	-0.0011761	-0.0084832	0.00821508	118	0.459691387
1949	0.00011009	-0.0049137	0.01279612	144	1
1950	0.00146932	-0.0060566	0.01514062	150	0.67916352
1951	-0.0013759	-0.0064897	0.01342401	155	0.870778741
1952	0.00430845	-0.0042234	0.01356849	155	0.623194498
1953	0.00204951	-0.0064177	0.01302943	155	0.567775488
1954	0.00441538	-0.0048905	0.01425092	154	0.362678763
1955	0.00199055	-0.0040263	0.01301402	144	0.491262458
1956	0.00550791	0.00086884	0.02385578	137	0.022743268
1957	0.00207882	-0.0064177	0.00957204	129	0.463488177
1958	0.00378217	-0.0052116	0.01127909	130	0.275253334
1959	0.00253151	-0.0009896	0.01301402	110	0.236901878
1960	0.00221332	-0.001494	0.01281727	92	0.38566942
1961	-0.0001509	-0.0057328	0.00442192	80	0.815121235
1962	-0.0005049	-0.0068796	0.00603875	79	0.723948146
1963	0.00022975	-0.0057009	0.00428392	77	0.635307642
1964	0.0004082	-0.0051874	0.00395503	69	0.707980754
1965	0.00096764	-0.0049052	0.00360541	62	0.59664176
1966	-0.0003541	-0.004232	0.00244114	64	0.794843654
1967	-0.0002175	-0.0038825	0.00260157	64	1
1968	-0.0005049	-0.005833	0.00145838	64	0.434992805
1969	-0.0003783	-0.0049554	0.00122525	72	0.328432063
1970	-0.0029096	-0.0076781	0	96	0.044597525
1971	-0.002937	-0.0061232	-0.0001028	119	0.030776324

1972	-0.0019957	-0.0046484	-0.0004867	153	0.030481815
1973	-0.0007964	-0.0039846	0.00156613	191	0.266142029
1974	-0.001385	-0.004222	0.00139135	230	0.156670912
1975	-0.0035476	-0.0103021	-0.0005049	282	0.020809235
1976	-0.001792	-0.0052696	0.00148754	353	0.305635671
1977	-0.0023576	-0.0061232	0.00096599	451	0.126596233
1978	-0.0036979	-0.0064508	-0.0007087	596	0.010045082
1979	-0.005983	-0.0105332	-0.0029088	752	8.92E-06
1980	-0.0063974	-0.0114284	-0.0028392	907	6.90E-06
1981	-0.0064574	-0.010769	-0.002891	1044	1.81E-05
1982	-0.0051218	-0.0081704	-0.0022431	1144	8.28E-05
1983	-0.0026603	-0.0043107	-0.0010387	1581	0.001359885
1984	-0.0026923	-0.0043107	-0.0015725	1667	1.09E-05
1985	-0.0018699	-0.0028913	-0.0005425	1685	0.005139834
1986	-0.0017711	-0.0025819	-0.0010124	1687	0.00011742
1987	-0.0015482	-0.0022979	-0.0008454	1698	1.46E-05
1988	-0.0014081	-0.0021103	-0.0005393	1677	0.000424139
1989	-0.0013948	-0.0020766	-0.0005538	1646	0.000304441
1990	-0.0017749	-0.0026495	-0.0010436	1597	3.36E-06
1991	-0.0013052	-0.0018658	-0.000566	1581	0.000979624
1992	-0.0014375	-0.0020293	-0.000585	1613	0.001450082
1993	-0.0014711	-0.0020986	-0.0007153	1669	0.000120898
1994	-0.0011826	-0.0019508	-0.0006685	1727	0.000256272
1995	-0.0010304	-0.001692	-0.0002643	1771	0.002388894
1996	-0.0012229	-0.0021269	-0.0004957	1768	0.000955797
1997	-0.0011659	-0.0019397	-0.0003423	2231	0.000723582
1998	-0.000795	-0.0015404	-0.0001246	2865	0.00736088
1999	-0.000747	-0.0014506	-2.64E-18	2970	0.034397664
2000	-0.0004322	-0.0012256	0.00030918	2748	0.369072843
2001	-0.0018438	-0.0028329	-0.0007447	1909	0.00020265
2002	-0.0019939	-0.0032318	-0.0007135	1158	0.001473065
2003	-0.0043495	-0.0057528	-0.0028568	1080	1.18E-11
2004	-0.0130206	-0.0157676	-0.0100467	616	5.82E-18
2005	-0.0080302	-0.0114746	-0.0054163	553	3.67E-09
2006	-0.0026482	-0.0054157	-0.0013212	238	0.002246735
2007	-0.0013871	-0.0033727	0.00062193	178	0.260829335
2008	-0.0040414	-0.0061697	0.00020644	137	0.059767982
2009	-0.0041653	-0.0068375	0.00273802	204	0.141293528
2010	-0.0041967	-0.006036	0.00038468	194	0.052283118
2011	-0.0025189	-0.0075965	0.00158262	58	0.511842308
2012	-0.0034463	-0.0198769	0.0067961	16	0.803619385
2013	-9.52E-05	-0.0199252	0.02026025	14	1
2014	-0.013714	-0.029904	0.02306764	14	0.423950195

404 **Extended Data Fig. 1.** Robustness of our results to different metrics of community similarity
 405 based on five-year lags. The computation of Distance Matrices for binary data were based on
 406 the similarity matrices available in the ade4 R package. Next to the name we include for each
 407 metric the pair '(Script ID: Coefficient ID)' based on the numbering by Gower & Legendre
 408 (1986). The metrics produced overall similar patterns in the variation in the change of turnover
 409 rate depending on breakpoint year

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412 **Extended Data Fig. 2:** Results of repeating our analysis when increasing the maximum lag included to compute turnover rates from the
 413 dependence of community similarity on lag.

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415 **Extended Data Fig. 3:** Same as Extended Data Fig. 2, but after omitting from the published data partitioning protocol^{1,2} a step filtering for ‘sample

416 completeness’, demonstrating that the impact of this step on our results is small.